

1 **BS-CLAY1: Anisotropic bounding surface constitutive model for**
2 **natural clays**

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4 **Abstract**

5 In this paper, a multi-surface anisotropic constitutive model is proposed for clayey soils, based
6 on bounding surface theory and a classical anisotropic critical state-based model. In the
7 proposed model, in addition to volumetric hardening law, rotational hardening rule is also
8 incorporated into the bounding surface formulation with a non-associated flow rule. The model
9 uses the bounding surface plasticity theory to produce a more realistic representation of the
10 nonlinear behavior of clays with high overconsolidation ratios. The detailed model formulation
11 is presented including an innovative approach for finding image stress points on the bounding
12 surface which offers an original conception of changing the projection center even at the
13 absence of plastic loading. Moreover, a modification procedure is discussed to improve the
14 performance of the proposed model for simulating the highly overconsolidated clays. The
15 proposed modifications besides the novel mapping rule form a novel framework that improves
16 the simulation capabilities of the models with elliptical yield/bounding surfaces, particularly in
17 the case of highly overconsolidated clays, and is applicable to all constitutive models with
18 elliptical yield/bounding surfaces. Furthermore, the efficiency of the framework is

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19 demonstrated by comparing the simulation results against element test data from a number of
20 different clays at lightly to highly overconsolidated conditions. The new model shows
21 promising capability in capturing important aspects of natural clays response during straining,
22 in particular the combined effects of small strain nonlinearity with fabric orientation.

23 **1. Introduction**

24 The modified Cam-clay (MCC) model (Roscoe and Burland, 1968) is one of the early
25 constitutive models developed within the critical state soil mechanics (CSSM) framework to
26 enhance the prediction of soft soils behavior, and hence improve the reliability of geotechnical
27 design on soils. An ellipsoid yield surface (YS) was adopted for this isotropic elastoplastic
28 model, and using an associated flow rule it has been able to reasonably replicate many of
29 experimentally observed responses of soft clays. However, natural clay is an intrinsically
30 anisotropic material; this anisotropy may be due to (1) the original structure of the soil fabric
31 (structural anisotropy), (2) the initial stress conditions (inherent anisotropy), and/or (3) the
32 current stress conditions of the soil (stress-induced anisotropy). Furthermore, there are
33 significant amounts of bonding among soil particles that form their natural structure, the
34 degradation and erasure of these bonds during straining strongly influence on their overall
35 behavior. Additionally, MCC assumes a purely linear elastic behavior within the YS. Such an
36 assumption infers an abrupt transition from elastic to plastic strains which is contradictory to
37 experimental observations. Using such a simplistic isotropic elastoplastic constitutive model
38 for practical applications is associated with a number of unrealistic initial assumptions which
39 can result in inaccurate modeling results.

40 It is a well-established fact that the yield points obtained from tests on undisturbed
41 specimens of natural clay constitute yield surfaces that are inclined in the representative stress
42 spaces. This inclination of the yield surfaces is largely agreed to be due to the inherent fabric

43 anisotropy that exists in the structure of the clay (Dafalias, 1986a; Graham et al., 1983;
44 Nishimura et al., 2007; Wheeler et al., 1999). Given the above, a popular approach in
45 considering the effects of soil anisotropy within a modeling framework has been the
46 development of elastoplastic soil constitutive models that involve inclined yield curves
47 (Sivasithamparam and Rezaia, 2017). This methodology for representing the inherent
48 anisotropy has its roots in the works of Sekiguchi (1977) and Hashiguchi (1977) and was
49 subsequently followed by other researchers such as Banerjee and Yousif (1986), Anandarajah
50 and Dafalias (1986), Dafalias (1986a), Whittle and Kavvas (1994), Ling et al. (2002),
51 Wheeler et al. (2003), Dafalias et al. (2006), Jiang et al. (2012), Karstunen et al. (2013),
52 Rezaia et al. (2014), Yang et al. (2015a, b), Sivasithamparam and Castro (2016), Karstunen
53 et al. (2015), Coombs (2017), Nieto Leal et al. (2018), Rezaia et al. (2017a, b), Rezaia et al.
54 (2018), Chen and Yang (2020). In these works, the rotated YS is either fixed (Sekiguchi &
55 Ohta, 1977; Zhou et al., 2005) or it can change its inclination by adopting a rotational hardening
56 (RH) rule to simulate the development or erasure of anisotropy during plastic straining (Chen
57 and Yang, 2020; Dafalias et al., 2020; Dafalias and Taiebat, 2014; Dafalias and Taiebat, 2013;
58 Dafalias et al., 2006; Wheeler et al., 2003; Yang et al., 2015a, b)

59 S-CLAY1 model (Wheeler et al., 2003) is an extension of the MCC model with an inclined
60 YS and a simple RH rule to simulate the anisotropic response of soft clays at large plastic
61 strains. Unlike most of the present anisotropic models with an inclined YS where RH rule is
62 only related to plastic volumetric strains (Dafalias and Taiebat, 2014; Dafalias and Taiebat,
63 2013; Dafalias et al., 2006; Ling et al., 2002) or plastic deviatoric strains (Chen and Yang,
64 2020), in S-CLAY1 the RH rule is related to both plastic volumetric strains and the plastic
65 shear strains. Some of the main advantages of this model are its relatively simple formulation,
66 realistic K_0 prediction, and simple determination of model parameters values from standard
67 laboratory tests (Rezaia et al., 2016), and due to the RH rule formulation, the uniqueness of

68 the critical state line (CSL) is preserved (Dafalias and Taiebat, 2013). This model is intended
69 for use with normally consolidated (NC) to lightly overconsolidated (LOC) soft clays, where
70 even a small increase of stress is likely to cause yielding. Moreover, a number of extensions
71 have branched out from this model. Besides the Creep-SCLAY1 (Sivasithamparam et al.,
72 2015) which was developed to consider creep behavior of natural clays and E-SCLAY1S
73 (Sivasithamparam and Castro, 2016) with a new YS based on the framework of logarithmic
74 contractancy, S-CLAY1S (Yildiz et al., 2009) is the most well-known extension of this basic
75 anisotropic model. While S-CLAY1 can capture the effects of plastic anisotropy, it is not
76 applicable for the analysis of natural clays that exhibit a considerable degree of structural
77 sensitivity. For an accurate prediction of the responses of structured sensitive clays, within the
78 constitutive model framework, the effects of bonding and loading-induced destructuration must
79 be taken into account. Using the concept of intrinsic yield surface (Gens and Nova, 1993)
80 because of its practical simplicity, Karstunen et al. (2005) extended the S-CLAY1 model to S-
81 CLAY1S to allow for the effects of soil structure. In the new model, the effect of the initial
82 structure is represented by the difference between the size of the YS of the natural soil and the
83 size of the YS when all of the internal structure/bonding of the soil is destroyed (i.e., the
84 intrinsic YS). In this model, an additional hardening law has been considered to describe the
85 destructuration evolution with plastic straining. However, similar to most classical elastoplastic
86 models, S-CLAY1S only returns elastic strains for the stress states inside the YS which, like
87 its simpler preceding version, restricts its application to simulation of the responses of NC to
88 LOC natural clays under monotonic loading conditions.

89 To allow for plastic strains at stress states within the YS, different theories have been
90 proposed. The bounding surface (BS) concept is one of the theories which has been widely
91 used to model nonlinear kinematic hardening (Ottosen and Ristinmaa, 2005). This concept was
92 first proposed simultaneously by Dafalias and Popov (1975, 1976) and Krieg (1975) for

93 simulation of cyclic behavior of metals, and was later extended to geomaterials by Anandarajah
94 and Dafalias (1986), Dafalias and Herrmann (1986) and Dafalias (1986b). A detailed
95 description of the mathematical formulation and application of BS plasticity theory in isotropic
96 and anisotropic constitutive models are provided in the abovementioned works. Based on the
97 BS concept, the classical YS can be replaced with a BS on which the actual stress points are
98 mapped to as imaginary stress points. The distance between the real stress points and their
99 corresponding so-called image points are used for the evaluation of the plastic moduli of the
100 actual stress states. To map the real stress points onto the BS, a projection center (PC) is needed.
101 Different methods have been employed to set the location of the PC. Dafalias and Herrmann
102 (1986) considered it to be along the induced hydrostatic line, Whittle and Kavvas (1994) and
103 Crouch et al. (1994) set PC at the origin of the stress space and Ling et al. (2002) assumed it to
104 be along the K_0 line. Nevertheless, due to its relative simplicity and attractive features, the BS
105 methodology has been rather popular among soil modelers to develop new or extended soil
106 constitutive models (e.g. Chakraborty et al., 2013; Seidalinov and Taiebat, 2014).

107 In the present work, the BS theory is used to further extend the S-CLAY1 model resulting
108 in a new soil constitutive model which is named the modified BS-CLAY1. The layout of the
109 paper is as follows. In Section 2, the general formulation of the proposed model and its
110 associated hardening rules, plastic modulus, and mapping rule are discussed. Also, in this
111 section, a simplified and a modified approach to specify the PC for the new model are proposed
112 and examined. The disadvantages associated with elliptical BS for simulating the highly
113 overconsolidated (HOC) samples is discussed in Section 3, and as solutions, two modifications
114 are presented and discussed. Section 4 describes the numerical implementation of the model.
115 To determine the effect of model parameters on the model predictions, sensitivity analyses are
116 performed in Section 5. In the following section, the model performance is verified against the

117 test data of a number of clays including kaolin clay, Lower Cromer till, and Boston blue clay.
118 Finally, a concise conclusion is provided in Section 7.

119 2. Model formulation

120 BS-CLAY1 is an extension of the S-CLAY1 model which can capture the nonlinearities in
121 the elastic domain while it also accounts for fabric anisotropy of natural clays. The new model
122 employs the same elastic formulation and hardening rules as in the original model. In the
123 following parts, the main components of the proposed model are presented in the general stress
124 space.

125 2.1. Bounding and loading surfaces

126 Bounding and loading surfaces are the two important components of the BS plasticity
127 theory. BS or preconsolidation surface is analogous to the YS in classical plasticity theory and
128 it represents the largest pressure that soil elements have experienced during their loading
129 history. The loading surface, on the other hand, is an imaginary surface that carries the stress
130 state. This surface is identical in shape and always smaller or equal in size to the BS; however,
131 no explicit definition is required for that.

132 The BS-CLAY1 uses the same YS of the S-CLAY1 model as the BS to facilitate the
133 application of an associated flow rule for determining the plastic strain rate direction. Eq. (1)
134 expresses the BS in the general stress space as

$$F = \frac{3}{2} \bar{s}_{ij} \bar{s}_{ij} - \frac{1}{3} (M^2 - \alpha^2) \left[\bar{p}'_m - \frac{1}{3} \bar{\sigma}_{kk} \right] \bar{\sigma}_{kk} = 0 \quad (1)$$

135 in which

$$\bar{\sigma}_{ij} = \bar{\sigma}_{ij}^d - \frac{1}{3} \alpha_{ij}^d \bar{\sigma}_{kk} \quad (2)$$

136 where $\bar{\sigma}_{ij}^d$ is the deviatoric stress tensor ($\bar{\quad}$ sign denotes the association of the variable to the
 137 BS), and α_{ij}^d is the deviatoric fabric tensor with the same form as the deviatoric stress tensor.
 138 \bar{p}'_m represents the size of BS for the natural clay that represents the maximum pressure that the
 139 soil sample has experienced in the past (i.e. preconsolidation pressure). M is the critical stress
 140 ratio in compression and scalar $\alpha = \sqrt{(3/2)\alpha_{ij}^d\alpha_{ij}^d}$. Fig. 1 shows the schematics of the
 141 bounding and loading surfaces of the BS-CLAY1 model in the triaxial stress space. In this
 142 figure, IS and SS refer to an image stress point and stress state, respectively.

Fig. 1. Schematics of bounding and loading surfaces in BS-CLAY1 model

2.2. Hardening rules

144 The new anisotropic BS model adopts isotropic and rotational hardening rules similar to
 145 those of the S-CLAY1 model to represent any changes in the size and the inclination of the BS
 146 due to plastic volumetric and shear strains. It should be noted that no hardening rule is assigned
 147 to the loading surface, and it is formed in a way that represents the stress state and changes by
 148 stress increments.

149 **2.2.1. Isotropic hardening rule**

150 For the expansion of the BS, the model adopts an isotropic hardening rule with the same
151 general formulation of that of the MCC model where the changes in the size of the BS are
152 related to the plastic volumetric strain increments, $d\varepsilon_v^p$, as

$$d\bar{p}'_m = \frac{v\bar{p}'_m}{\lambda - \kappa} d\varepsilon_v^p \quad (3)$$

153 in which v is the specific volume, and λ and κ are the slopes of the normal compression and
154 swelling lines in the $(\ln p' - v)$ space, respectively.

155 **2.2.2. Rotational hardening rule**

156 As stated above, the proposed model belongs to the class of anisotropic models where
157 anisotropy is introduced through the initial inclination of the YS (BS in this case) and the
158 kinematic hardening of BS, in terms of its change of inclination during large straining, is
159 captured using an RH rule. In this work, an RH rule, similar to that of the S-CLAY1 model, is
160 employed to describe the rotation of the BS due to the anisotropy. The RH formulation
161 represents the development and erasure of anisotropy due to both plastic volumetric and shear
162 strain increments. In the general stress space, this hardening rule has the form

$$d\alpha_{ij}^d = \mu \left(\left[\frac{3\bar{\sigma}_{ij}^d}{4\bar{p}'} - \alpha_{ij}^d \right] \langle d\varepsilon_v^p \rangle + \beta \left[\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{ij}^d}{3\bar{p}'} - \alpha_{ij}^d \right] d\varepsilon_d^p \right) \quad (4)$$

163 in which $d\varepsilon_d^p$ is the increment of plastic deviatoric strain. The RH rule has two soil constants, μ
164 and β , where the first one controls the absolute rate at which the deviatoric fabric tensor
165 approaches toward its current target value and the latter controls the relative effect of $d\varepsilon_d^p$ and
166 $d\varepsilon_v^p$ in rotating the BS. Macaulay brackets $\langle \rangle$ are used so that only the positive $d\varepsilon_v^p$ values
167 are taken into account. The RH formulation of Eq. (4) has been argued not to prevent the

168 excessive rotation of the YS for numerical simulations where stress ratio (η) is significantly
 169 higher than the critical stress ratio (Dafalias and Taiebat, 2013); however, it has been proven
 170 to be practical for common loading applications (e.g., Rezania et al. (2017a, b) and Karstunen
 171 et al. (2015)) and hence adopted in this work in order to keep the developed model within the
 172 hierarchical extension of the basic model.

173 2.3. Plastic modulus of the bounding surface

174 At this stage of the model development, the associated flow rule is adopted for the BS-
 175 CLAY1 model. It means that the BS also represents the plastic potential function (i.e., $G = F$).
 176 However, in section 3 adoption of the non-associated flow rule in the model is also considered,
 177 and the corresponding improved model performance for the HOC samples are discussed.
 178 Accordingly, the plastic strain increment is determined as

$$d\varepsilon_{ij}^p = \langle L \rangle \frac{\partial G}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{ij}} \quad (5)$$

179 where L is the plastic loading index defined as

$$L = \frac{1}{\bar{K}_p} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{ij}} d\bar{\sigma}_{ij} = \frac{D_{klrs} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{rs}} d\varepsilon_{kl}}{\bar{K}_p + \frac{\partial F}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{ab}} D_{abcd} \frac{\partial G}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{cd}}} \quad (6)$$

180 in which \bar{K}_p is the plastic modulus of the BS and D_{klrs} is elastic stiffness tensor. To determine
 181 \bar{K}_p and establish a complete stress-strain relationship, the consistency condition should be
 182 satisfied over the BS. This guarantees that the stress state remains on the BS during plastic
 183 flow. Following a standard differentiation of the BS function (i.e., Eq. (1)) with regards to its
 184 state variables, the mathematical expression obtained from consistency condition reads as

$$dF = \frac{\partial F}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{ij}} d\bar{\sigma}_{ij} + \frac{\partial F}{\partial \alpha_{ij}^d} d\alpha_{ij}^d + \frac{\partial F}{\partial \bar{p}'_m} \frac{d\bar{p}'_m}{d\varepsilon_v^p} d\varepsilon_v^p = 0 \quad (7)$$

185 Substituting the hardening rules and loading index into Eq. (7), the plastic modulus of the BS
 186 is obtained as (refer to the Appendix for more details on the derivation procedure)

$$\bar{K}_p = -\frac{\partial F}{\partial \alpha_{ij}^d} \left(\frac{\partial \alpha_{ij}^d}{\partial \varepsilon_v^p} \left\langle \frac{\partial G}{\partial \bar{p}'} \right\rangle + \frac{\partial \alpha_{ij}^d}{\partial \varepsilon_d^p} \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \frac{\partial G}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{ij}^d} \frac{\partial G}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{ij}^d}} \right) - \frac{\partial F}{\partial \bar{p}'_m} \frac{v\bar{p}'_m}{\lambda - \kappa} \frac{\partial G}{\partial \bar{p}'_m} \quad (8)$$

187 2.4. Mapping rule

188 In the constitutive models modified with BS plasticity theory, the plastic modulus of the
 189 actual stress state on the loading surface, K_p , is related to plastic modulus of the image stress
 190 point on the bounding surface. Therefore, the plastic moduli of these two points are related to
 191 each other through sets of equations called shape hardening functions. In this work, a radial
 192 mapping rule is adopted to project the current stress state to an image stress point on the
 193 bounding surface.

$$K_p = \bar{K}_p + S_l \quad (9)$$

194 The shape hardening function, S_l , is defined as

$$S_l = \bar{p}'_m{}^3 h_l \times \frac{(1 - \rho^{\psi_1})}{\rho^{\psi_2}} \quad (10)$$

195 where S_l represents the shape hardening function for the loading condition. ψ_1 , ψ_2 and h_l are
 196 model parameters that control the relationship between loading surface and BS plastic moduli
 197 and influence the overall response of the model for the overconsolidated condition. ρ is the
 198 ratio of the relative distance of stress state (SS) and projection center (PC) to the relative
 199 distance of image stress point (IS) and PC (i.e. $\rho = |SS - PC|/|IS - PC|$) (see Fig. 2 and Fig.

200 4). As is clear, when the stress state reaches the BS (i.e. SS = IS), ρ becomes 1, and the
201 hardening shape function value tends to zero.

202 **2.4.1. Projection center**

203 To evaluate ρ , and determine the IS, and calculate the hardening shape function values, first
204 an appropriate PC must be found. In this section, two different methods of finding the PC,
205 which have been tested for the proposed model, are presented and discussed. To this end, the
206 BS is divided into a subcritical side and a supercritical side. The division is from the point at
207 which the CSL intersects the BS. It should be noted that for the development of the mapping
208 rule in the following, if the SS is located to the right of the vertical line passing through the
209 intersection point, it is referred to as a subcritical SS, and otherwise as a supercritical SS.

210 **2.4.1.1. Simple method**

211 For a simplified approach, the PC is assumed to be located at the origin of the stress space
212 and considered to be fixed during the loading procedure. As can be seen in Fig. 2, the loading
213 surface has a fixed point at the origin of the stress space, and its orientation is identical to the
214 BS, but with a different size (p_l). In this case, the following relationship can be used to find the
215 image stress point on the BS from the current SS

$$\bar{\sigma}_{ij} = \frac{1}{\rho} \times \sigma_{ij} \quad (11)$$

Fig. 2. Schematics of BS-CLAY1 model with projection center located at the origin of stress space

Hence in this approach ρ becomes the similarity ratio between bounding and loading surfaces, and it is identical to the ratio of the size of loading surface to the size of the bounding surface (p'_l/\bar{p}'_m). This simplified method is, therefore, an uncomplicated procedure for enhancing a single YS constitutive model with the BS plasticity theory. However, in this method, the accuracy and consistency of the results with the experimental observations are affected by increasing the overconsolidation ratio (OCR) of the soil. For instance, as illustrated in Fig. 3a, for an incremental undrained shearing of a LOC soil specimen, all of the SSs are located in the subcritical side of the BS and their corresponding ISs are also mapped onto this side of the BS. Therefore, based on the BS framework for such an undrained shearing scenario when all stress states, e.g., SS₁, SS₂, and SS₃, are located in the subcritical side, the stress path will continuously incline to the left toward the critical state that is, in fact, the expected response according to the experimental observations. However, for similar loading of a HOC soil, the SSs will be located on the supercritical side of the BS and consequently, as explained in the sequel, the simplified BS procedure will not result in an elegant stress path simulation. For example, if the undrained shearing of a stiff clay is considered (see Fig. 3b), following the simplified method the ISs corresponding to SS₁ and SS₂ are projected to the subcritical side,

232 and the stress state SS_3 is projected to the supercritical side of the BS. In fact, in this scenario
233 following the simplified method, the CSL acts as a dividing line. That is, all the SSs that are
234 located under the CSL are projected to the subcritical side and the SSs located over the CSL
235 will be projected to the supercritical side of the BS. This will cause the stress path to initially
236 tend to the left and then incline to the right when it crosses the CSL. Such behavior is not
237 observed in experimental studies on HOC clays where the undrained shearing stress path is
238 inclined to the right continuously from the beginning of loading. This implies that some
239 modifications in the definition of PC are required. In the following section, a modified method
240 is proposed and discussed.

Fig. 3. Simulation of stress paths for (a) LOC (b) HOC clay with the simplified method

241 **2.4.1.2. Modified method**

242 To resolve the pitfall of using the simplified method, in this work a number of different rules
243 for defining the PC have been examined. From the analyses, it was found that in order to
244 consistently better predict the experimentally observed loading paths in both LOC (i.e., soft)
245 and HOC (i.e., stiff) domains, the PC should be defined in such a way that the subcritical SSs
246 are projected to the subcritical side of the BS, and supercritical SSs are projected to the
247 supercritical side of the BS. To achieve this in the modified method, the PC is defined on the
248 α -line and it is assumed that it can freely move within the BS with the variations of the SS.
249 Similar concepts were also used in the literature (Ling et al., 2002; Seidalinov and Taiebat,
250 2014). By adopting a moving PC, the location of the projection center in the general stress
251 space (σ_{ij}^c) can be readily defined as a fraction of the size of the BS. To this end, using the
252 radial mapping rule the image stresses are related to the actual stresses through

$$\sigma_{ij}^c = \zeta \bar{p}'_m (\alpha_{ij}^d + \delta_{ij}) \quad (12)$$

253 In this equation, ζ is the parameter which, based on the current SS, changes the location of the
254 PC and is defined as

$$\zeta = \gamma_1 \left(1 - \frac{p'}{\bar{p}'_m} \right) \quad (13)$$

255 in which γ_1 is the model constant. Substituting Eq. (13) in Eq. (12), the PC is calculated as

$$\sigma_{ij}^c = \gamma_1 (\bar{p}'_m - p') (\alpha_{ij}^d + \delta_{ij}) \quad (14)$$

256 It must be considered that the PC shall always lay within the BS. Therefore, the parameter γ_1
257 should be limited to the following value

$$\gamma_{1,max} = \frac{\bar{p}'_m}{\bar{p}'_m - p'} \quad (15)$$

Eq. (14) implies that the location of the PC changes with the variations of SS, BS magnitude, and the degree of anisotropy. That is, contrary to the model proposed by Ling et al. (2002), even when the stress state varies inside the BS and has not intersected with it, the location of the PC can change. Based on the hardening laws used in the proposed model, the variations of PC are defined as

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij}^c = \gamma_1 \gamma_2 [(\dot{\bar{p}}'_m - \dot{p}')(\alpha_{ij}^d + \delta_{ij}) + (\bar{p}'_m - p')\dot{\alpha}_{ij}^d] \quad (16)$$

where γ_2 is applied to control the pace of PC variations. As will be shown in the parameter determination section, this parameter is considered less than 1, and therefore, the condition of being inside the BS is not violated for the PC. If $\gamma_1 = 0$, the PC moves to the origin of the stress space and the modified method turns back into the simplified method, and if γ_2 becomes zero, the PC remains fixed during the loading. To find the location of the IS on the BS, as shown in Fig. 4 for the triaxial stress space, the line passing through the PC and SS intersects with the BS which, depending on the location of SS, one of the two intersection points is selected as the IS. To find the image stress point, the following equations should be satisfied

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{p}' &= \frac{1}{\rho}(p' - p'_c) + p'_c \\ \bar{q} &= \frac{1}{\rho}(q - q_c) + q_c \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

where the subscript c in p'_c and q_c stands for the projection center. Fig. 5, shows the variations of PC during loading. It should be noted that by considering $\gamma_2 = 1$, the projection center is always located on the α -line and its location varies with the variations of SS; as a result, the stress path is invariably inclined to the right toward the critical state.

Fig. 4. Schematics of BS-CLAY1 model with modified projection center

Fig. 5. Simulation of stress paths for (a) LOC (b) HOC clay using modified projection method

275 **3. Discussion on the elliptical bounding surface deficiencies – problem statement**

276 Although elliptical BSs provide acceptable predictions for NC and LOC clays with low
277 computational efforts, they are almost unable to properly simulate the behavior of HOC
278 samples properly. Since the BS theory enables the constitutive models to capture the nonlinear
279 behavior inside the BS, it cannot modify the peak strength associated with the bulky shape of
280 elliptical BSs. Therefore, there might be a significant deviation between simulated shear
281 strength and test data, and this divergence can be more notable with increasing the OCR. It is
282 noteworthy that in some cases, the bounding surface theory intensifies this discrepancy,
283 especially for $OCR > 2$. To address this, Fig. 6 demonstrates the comparison of stress paths
284 predicted by S-CLAY1 and BS-CLAY1 for an isotropically consolidated sample of Lower
285 Cromer till (Gens, 1982) with $OCR = 4$ (Table 1). As can be seen, the simulated stress path by
286 S-CLAY1 goes up vertically until it touches the yield surface, and then it changes its direction
287 toward the CSL due to softening and the RH rule makes it to follow the CSL until the
288 inclination of the BS reaches the equilibrium value of anisotropy. However, the BS-CLAY1
289 reproduces a nonlinear stress path that passes the CSL and tends to reach the CSL at higher
290 deviatoric stresses without touching the BS. Since the BS has a bulky elliptical shape, there is
291 considerable room for the stress path to continue its increments without triggering plastic
292 hardening rules. The overestimated peak shear strength of HOC clays besides the
293 unsatisfactory performance in capturing the yield points convinced researchers to use yield
294 surfaces with different shapes, i.e. teardrop-shaped surfaces (Chen and Yang, 2017; Chen and
295 Yang, 2020; Collins and Kelly, 2002; Collins and Hilder, 2002; Lagioia et al., 1996; Taiebat
296 and Dafalias, 2010). Since the S-CLAY1 employs an elliptical YS and modifying the shape of
297 the YS is out of the scope of this paper, possible solutions for improving the estimation of the
298 peak shear strength of HOC samples are presented in the subsequent sections.

Fig. 6. Comparison of S-CLAY1 and BS-CLAY1 for undrained triaxial test on HOC sample

299 3.1. Problem solutions

300 In order to improve the prediction of peak strength of HOC samples, a step-by-step
301 procedure is taken into account. In the first step, a non-associated flow rule is adopted to the
302 proposed model. This stage is followed by introducing modified hardening rules that are used
303 while the stress state is located inside the BS. In each step, the effect of the modifications is
304 illustrated using a comparison of simulated stress paths with the experimental data result of an
305 undrained triaxial test on the sample of Lower Cromer till.

306 3.1.1. Non-associated flow rule

307 Although some studies (Yu, 1998; Jiang and Ling, 2010; Jiang et al., 2012) suggest that
308 using associated flow rule is a feasible assumption for constitutive models with an oriented YS,
309 it was found that employing non-associated flow rule leads to more realistic simulations (Yu,
310 1998). In the case of the HOC clays, the non-associated flow rule provides the opportunity to
311 define slender BS to shrink the elastic domain. In addition to improving the simulation
312 capabilities for NC samples, this contraction helps the stress path to reach to CSL at lower
313 deviatoric stress, and it relatively modifies the overestimated peak strength.

314 To establish the non-associated flow rule formulation, the BS in Eq. 1 should be rewritten
 315 in the following form

$$F = \frac{3}{2} \bar{s}_{ij} \bar{s}_{ij} - \frac{1}{3} (N^2 - \alpha^2) \left[\bar{p}'_m - \frac{1}{3} \bar{\sigma}_{kk} \right] \bar{\sigma}_{kk} = 0 \quad (18)$$

316 where the M is replaced with a constant yield surface shape factor, N . A similar oriented and
 317 sheared elliptical surface with different size is also used for the plastic potential surface (PPS)

$$G = \frac{3}{2} \bar{s}_{ij} \bar{s}_{ij} - \frac{1}{3} (M^2 - \beta^2) \left[\bar{p}'_g - \frac{1}{3} \bar{\sigma}_{kk} \right] \bar{\sigma}_{kk} = 0 \quad (19)$$

318 where β and \bar{p}'_g represent the inclination and the size of the PPS, respectively. The proposed
 319 model does not employ any rotational hardening rule for the plastic potential surface, and it
 320 assumes an identical inclination for the BS and the PPS ($\alpha = \beta$).

321 Fig. 7a shows the effect of considering the non-associated flow rule on the response of the
 322 model in simulating the behavior of HOC clay. As can be seen, although employing the non-
 323 associated flow rule has a significant impact on model performance and the peak strength
 324 estimation, the model needs more modifications to reproduce more accurate predictions.

Fig. 7. Effects of modifications on the model response, (a) effect of non-associated flow rule, and
 (b) modified hardening rule

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3.1.2. Modified hardening rules

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The main idea of this modification is to change the size and inclination of the BS while the SS varies inside the BS. This variation should be such that the SS of the HOC sample touches the BS sooner. To this end, specific hardening rules are adopted to the model which drag the BS towards the SS for HOC samples and virtually tighten the elastic domain. Therefore, the following modified hardening rules are defined to adjust the BS based on the plastic strain increments that are determined using the gradients of BS and PPS at the IS and the plastic modulus of the current SS, (K_p)

$$d\bar{p}'_m = A \left(\frac{\bar{p}'_m}{p'} \right)^2 \frac{v\bar{p}'_m}{\lambda - \kappa} d\varepsilon_v^p \quad (20)$$

$$d\alpha_{ij}^d = A \left(\frac{\bar{p}'_m}{p'} \right)^2 \mu \left(\left[\frac{3\bar{\sigma}_{ij}^d}{4\bar{p}'} - \alpha_{ij}^d \right] \langle d\varepsilon_v^p \rangle + \beta \left[\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{ij}^d}{3\bar{p}'} - \alpha_{ij}^d \right] d\varepsilon_d^p \right) \quad (21)$$

$$A = \frac{\langle OCR - 2 \rangle}{OCR - 2} = \begin{cases} 1 & OCR > 2 \\ 0 & OCR \leq 2 \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

334 which the term $\left(\frac{\bar{p}'_m}{p'}\right)^2$ is considered to amplify the effect of modified hardening rules with
335 increasing the OCR , and A is a constant parameter that vanishes the modified hardening rule
336 for $OCR \leq 2$. As the modified mapping rule projects the IS on the dry side of the CSL, the
337 modified hardening rules reproduce softening-like behavior associated with HOC samples.

338 Fig. 7b shows the effect of using both non-associated flow rule and modified hardening rule
339 on the model simulations. As can be seen, the modified hardening rule improves the predictions
340 significantly, and the model response fits very well with experimental data. Although the most
341 logical way to capture the peak shear strength of HOC samples more accurately is using the
342 teardrop-shaped yield/bounding surface, using the proposed modified hardening rules
343 associated with BS theory and proper mapping rule can enhance the elliptical BS to replicate
344 the peak strength with the desired accuracy level.

345 4. Numerical implementation

346 In this implementation, the plastic strain components associated with the BS evolution can
347 be obtained using the Euler backward implicit integration scheme. For this purpose, the plastic
348 multiplier or plastic loading index (Eq. 6) can be rewritten in terms of BS value as

$$L = \frac{F}{\bar{K}_p + \frac{\partial F}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{ij}} D_{ijkl} \frac{\partial G}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{kl}}} \quad (23)$$

349 Using the Euler backward implicit integration scheme, the occurrence of plastic strains is
350 guaranteed while the prescribed convergence criterion for the iterative stress integration with
351 respect to the BS is satisfied (i.e. $F < 10^{-7}$). Under this condition, the trial stress in step ($n +$
352 1) can be obtained from stresses at the previous step (i.e., step n) as follow

$$\sigma_{ij}^{(n+1)} = \sigma_{ij}^{(n)} + d\sigma_{ij} \quad (24)$$

353 where the stress increment is calculated as

$$d\sigma_{ij} = D_{ijkl}d\varepsilon_{kl}^e = D_{ijkl}(d\varepsilon_{kl} - L D_{klmn} \frac{\partial G}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{mn}}) \quad (25)$$

354 In order to obtain stable solutions, if necessary, the size of the strain increment can be
 355 controlled through sub-stepping. It should be noted that for the stress states inside the BS, an
 356 explicit Euler Forward integration scheme is employed for the stress integration. A summary
 357 of the implementation algorithm for the proposed model is presented in Fig. 8.

```

READ: Initial stress state( $\sigma_{ij}^0$ ), state variables, strain increment( $d\varepsilon_{ij}$ )
IF (strain increment subdivision is required) THEN
    Determine sub increment number ( $N_{sub}$ )
    Subdivide strain increment:  $d\varepsilon_{ij}^{sub} = d\varepsilon_{ij}/N_{sub}$ 
END IF

DO n=1,  $N_{sub}$ 
    Trial strain increment:  $d\varepsilon_{ij}^{trial} = d\varepsilon_{ij}^{sub}$ 
    Convergence criteria: FALSE
    DO WHILE (Not converged)
        Convergence criteria: TRUE
        Image stress point:  $\bar{\sigma}_{ij}$ 
        Plastic modulus of bounding surface:  $\bar{K}_p$ 
        Shape hardening function:  $S_l$ 
        Plastic modulus of loading surface:  $K_p = \bar{K}_p + S_l$ 
        Explicit plastic loading index (plastic multiplier):  $L$ 
        Plastic strain increment based on BS and PPS gradient at image stress point:  $d\varepsilon_{ij}^{plastic,IS}$ 
        Elastoplastic stiffness tensor:  $D_{ijkl}^{ep}$ 
         $d\sigma_{ij}^{trial(n)} = D_{ijkl}^{ep}d\varepsilon_{kl}^{trial(n)}$ 
         $\sigma_{ij}^{trial(n)} = \sigma_{ij}^0 + d\sigma_{ij}^{trial(n)}$ 
        Calculate: Bounding surface value:  $F$ 
        IF ( $F > 10^{-7}$ ) THEN
            Plastic modulus of bounding surface:  $K_p = \bar{K}_p$ 
            Implicit plastic loading index (plastic multiplier):  $L$ 
            Plastic strain increment:  $d\varepsilon_{ij}^{plastic}$ 
            Convergence criteria: FALSE
        END IF
        Update stress variable
    END DO
END DO
END DO
    
```

Fig. 8. Implementation algorithm for the BS-CLAY1

358 5. Model parameters

359 The input soil constants and state variables required for the proposed model can be
360 categorized into the following four groups: (1) isotropic parameters including \bar{p}'_m , e_0 (initial
361 void ratio), M , N , λ , κ and ν (Poisson's ratio) which are similar to those of the MCC model,
362 (2) anisotropy parameters including α_0 (initial value of α), μ and β , and (3) BS plasticity
363 parameters γ_1 , γ_2 , h_l , ψ_1 , and ψ_2 . The evaluation of the isotropic parameters is straightforward
364 and they can be determined from the results of standard geotechnical tests as is the routine for
365 MCC-based critical state models (see, for example, Muir Wood, 1990). The N parameter can
366 be calibrated by both fitting the BS to yield stress points in stress space and by using the
367 experimental data results of the undrained triaxial tests.

368 In theory, the initial orientation of the clay fabric should be represented in a tensorial form
369 with independent components; however, for practical simplicity, clay's initial fabric
370 orientation is commonly considered to be of cross-anisotropic nature which is a realistic
371 assumption as natural clays have generally been deposited only one-dimensionally in a vertical
372 direction (Rezania et al., 2014; Sivasithamparam and Rezania, 2017). With this assumption,
373 determination of the components of initial fabric tensor is significantly simplified as they can
374 now be computed using a scalar α_0 which represents the initial inclination of the BS. Where
375 enough experimental data are available for yield stress points from triaxial tests under different
376 stress paths, the value of α_0 can be readily calibrated. However, as this is not often the case, it
377 is reasonable to assume that the initial inclination of BS has been developed under K_0
378 (coefficient of earth pressure at rest) loading, based on this assumption Wheeler et al. (2003)
379 proposed the following closed-form relationships for determination of α_0 and β

$$\alpha_0 = \frac{\eta_{K_0}^2 + 3\eta_{K_0} - M^2}{3} \quad (26)$$

380 and

$$\beta = \frac{3(4M^2 - 4\eta_{K_0}^2 - 3\eta_{K_0})}{8(\eta_{K_0}^2 - M^2 + 2\eta_{K_0})} \quad (27)$$

381 where η_{K_0} is the ratio of deviatoric to mean effective stress at K_0 condition (i.e., $\eta_{K_0} =$
382 $3(1 - K_0)/(1 + 2K_0)$). The value of K_0 can be measured, or estimated using Jaky's formula
383 for NC soils (i.e., $K_0 \approx 1 - \sin \phi'$, with ϕ' being the soil friction angle at critical state) or
384 Mayne and Kulhawy's (1982) formula for overconsolidated soils (i.e., $K_0 \approx (1 -$
385 $\sin \phi')OCR^{\sin \phi'}$). Given the dependence of K_0 and M to ϕ' (e.g., $M = 6 \sin \phi' / (3 - \sin \phi')$),
386 Wheeler et al. (2003) suggested that for NC to LOC soils α_0 and β are uniquely related to ϕ' .
387 However, based on the authors' experience, Eqs. (26) and (27) yield reasonable prediction
388 results for overconsolidated soils, as well. The other anisotropy constant, μ , can be best
389 evaluated by calibrating against experimentally observed data, for example from specialized
390 multi-stage loading-unloading-reloading stress path triaxial tests where different loading stages
391 involve a major change in the stress path direction that facilitates excessive rotation of the BS.
392 As such loadings are not typical in practical conditions, it is safe to assume that model
393 performance is not particularly sensitive to the values of μ ; hence, for its determination,
394 calibration against standard isotropic compression test data should suffice. It should be noted
395 that, based on experimental verifications, Wheeler et al. (2003) suggested that the value of β
396 should be between $0.5M$ and M , and Zentar et al. (2002) suggested that the value of μ should
397 normally lie in the range $10/\lambda$ and $15/\lambda$.

398 The sensitivities of model predictions on the values of BS parameters, h_l , ψ_1 , ψ_2 , γ_1 and
399 γ_2 are illustrated in Fig. 9. Fig. 9a shows that increasing the parameter h_l clearly influences the

400 behavior predicted by the model for both LOC and HOC conditions. As Fig. 9b shows,
401 changing ψ_1 also makes notable changes on model prediction; however, its effect on the
402 prediction of HOC samples is not as bold as h_l and happens within a smaller range of plausible
403 values. These trends can be explained by looking at Eq. (10) when these parameters' values
404 approach very large numbers, i.e. infinity. For h_l , as its value tends toward infinity the limit of
405 Eq. (10) tends toward infinity too. Hence, the proposed model reduces to a standard
406 elastoplastic model and predicts the soil behavior similar to S-CLAY1. On the other hand,
407 when ψ_1 tends to infinity Eq. (10) results in a value which is a function of h_l and ψ_2 (re-written
408 in Eq. (28)), not necessarily a large number. Fig. 9b shows that as ψ_1 increases, the model
409 shows less sensitivity to its variations.

$$\lim_{\psi_1 \rightarrow \infty} S_l = \frac{\bar{p}_m'^3 h_l}{\rho \psi_2} \quad (28)$$

410 Fig. 9c shows the effects of changing ψ_2 values on model predictions. This parameter,
411 similar to h_l , can cause significant effects on the model response. However, unlike h_l , it can
412 bring the effects of the existence of an elastic core into the model predictions. It can be
413 explained by the limit of Eq. (10) when ψ_2 approach infinity. In this case, the limit of the Eq.
414 (10), first rapidly tends toward infinity and as the loading process progresses and ρ increases,
415 its pace toward infinity decreases. Consequently, for the early parts of the stress path, the
416 predicted behavior resembles that of the standard elastoplastic models, and as ψ_2 continues to
417 increase, the BS effects on model predictions becomes pronounced. The effect of parameter
418 γ_1 , for LOC and HOC conditions, is shown in Fig. 9d. As can be seen, when the soil is lightly
419 overconsolidated, γ_1 has negligible effects on the results, while for the HOC soils, the
420 variations of γ_1 have notable effects on the model response. Therefore, this parameter can be
421 used for the calibration of the model at HOC conditions .However, it should be kept in mind

422 that high values of γ_1 can reproduce anomalies, i.e. $\gamma_1 = 1$ in Fig. 9d, due to the improper
423 projected image points and the pace of PC evolutions. Moreover, the main reason for the
424 different model response by considering $\gamma_1 = 0.25$ is that unlike other values of γ_1 , this value
425 results in the projection center on the left side of the SS, and hence, the ISs are located on the
426 subcritical side of the BS. Therefore, it is noteworthy that suitable values should be assigned
427 to this parameter based on the OCR values. Fig. 9e shows how the variation of the γ_2 can affect
428 the model simulations slightly. As is clear, γ_2 have an insignificant influence on the model
429 predictions. The main role of this parameter is to control the SS to remain inside the BS during
430 softening behavior associated with newly define modified hardening rules by reducing the pace
431 of PC evolutions (Eqs. 20 and 21).

432 Although any real positive number can be assigned to shape hardening function parameters
433 (h_l , ψ_1 , and ψ_2), the model predictions and sensitivity analysis are evaluated to establish a
434 relationship between them to reduce the model constants without affecting simulation
435 capabilities. Regarding this, as reasonable responses are reproduced using the value of h_l
436 between 10 to 100, the authors suggest considering ψ_1 using the following equation

$$\psi_1 = \frac{h_l}{10} - 1 \quad (29)$$

437 and choosing ψ_2 between $0.5\psi_1$ to $1.5\psi_1$. A similar assessment procedure is conducted over
438 projection center parameters (γ_1 and γ_2). Since the position of the projection center is directly
439 related to the consolidation stress state and the OCR, attempts to correlate projection center
440 parameters to OCR lead to the following equations

$$\gamma_1 = \frac{2.5}{OCR} \quad (30)$$

$$\gamma_2 = \max\left\{\frac{2.0}{OCR}, 1\right\} \quad (31)$$

Fig. 9. Model sensitivity analysis with BS parameters: (a) h_l , (b) ψ_1 , (c) ψ_2 , (d) γ_1 , and (e) γ_2

441 6. Comparison with experimental data

442 In this section, the numerical performance of the newly proposed anisotropic BS model is
 443 verified using available element level experimental data from the literature. To this end, the
 444 compression triaxial test data for three different soils including Kaolin Clay (Banerjee et al.,
 445 1985), Boston blue clay (Ladd and Varallyay, 1965), and Lower Corner till (Gens, 1982) are
 446 used. Prior to the simulations, and following the procedures described in the previous section,
 447 the model parameters are first calibrated. For all three soil types, the parameter calibration has
 448 begun with the determination of anisotropy parameters using the experiments carried out at

449 OCR=1. Then the BS parameters are calibrated at higher OCRs. Table 1 summarizes the model
 450 parameter values for each soil type which are further discussed in the following.

Table 1. Initial values of the state variable and constants of the BS-CLAY1 model adopted for three types of clays

Parameter		Kaolin clay	Boston Blue clay	Lower Cromer till
Critical state and yield surface	e_0	0.94–1.07	1	1.79
	ν	0.2	0.227	0.258
	κ	0.05	0.036	0.009
	λ	0.14	0.184	0.63
	N	0.85	0.98	1.03
	M	1.05	1.35	1.18
Anisotropy	α_0	Variable	0.57	0.45
	μ	150	280	260
	β	0.57	0.30	0.74
Bounding surface	γ_1		2.5/OCR	
	γ_2		2.0/OCR	
	h_l	35	30	50
	ψ_1	2.5	2	4
	ψ_2	2.5	2	4

451 6.1. Kaolin clay

452 A series of undrained triaxial tests on fully saturated Kaolin clay samples were conducted
 453 by Stipho (1978). In his stress-controlled compression experiments on anisotropically
 454 consolidated samples ($K_0 = 0.8, 0.67, \text{ and } 0.57$), Stipho (1978) considered different OCR
 455 values ranging from 1.0 to 4.0. In these experiments, the preconsolidation stress \bar{p}'_m was 204
 456 kPa for anisotropically consolidated samples. The experimentally observed soil responses from
 457 these tests are used here to validate the prediction capability of the developed model. It is worth

458 mentioning that the initial rotations of the BS for different K_0 values are obtained from
459 Sivasithamparam and Castro (2015) by simulation of the K_0 stress paths.

460 Fig. 10 shows the simulation results obtained from the BS-CLAY1 model in comparison to
461 the test data. In these figures, the solid lines show the predicted results for compression tests.
462 As can be seen, the BS-CLAY1 model simulations are both qualitatively and quantitatively
463 consistent with the experimentally observed responses in the stress path and the stress-strain
464 spaces. Neglecting the inability of experimental data in capturing the failure properly, due to
465 stress-controlled nature of the tests (Sivasithamparam and Castro, 2015), at HOC conditions
466 (e.g., OCR=4), the simulations of the BS-CLAY1 model fit very well with the test results.

467 The comparisons for corresponding stress-strain (in terms of normalized deviatoric stress,
468 q/p'_m , versus axial strain, ε_1) are shown in Fig. 10. The performance of the proposed BS-
469 CLAY1 model is remarkably accurate for HOC samples. It correctly predicts a continuously
470 hardening response with no peaks, similar to what was experimentally observed (see, for
471 example, Figs. 10a, c, e).

Fig. 10. Comparison of BS-CLAY1 predictions for Kaolin clay

472 6.2. Boston blue clay

473 Boston Blue clay is a marine clay type that exists in a layer of the complex Boston soil
 474 deposit. The dry and saturated unit weights of this soil are $1826\text{--}1922\text{ kg/m}^3$ and $1281\text{--}1393$
 475 kg/m^3 , respectively. Moreover, the liquid limit, plasticity index, and liquidity index of Boston
 476 blue clay are 41%, 21%, and 0.8%, respectively. A series of undrained compression triaxial
 477 tests on anisotropically consolidated samples of Boston blue clay were performed by Ladd and
 478 Varallyay (1965) and Fayad (1986). The specimens were tested at $e_0=0.84\text{--}0.89$ with p'_m
 479 ranging from 273 to 785 kPa. The model parameter values, determined for simulations, are

480 summarized in Table 1 among which the values of conventional critical state parameters are
481 taken from Chen and Yang (2020).

482 Fig. 11 show the BS-CLAY1 predictions of normalized stress paths and corresponding
483 stress-strain curves for isotropically and anisotropically consolidated samples of Boston blue
484 clay, respectively. Fig. 11a shows that, excluding $OCR=2$, the stress path predictions are in
485 good agreement with experimental measurements. Moreover, the model responses are
486 promising in stress-strain space, despite the inability of the model to generate softening
487 behavior. Also, the numerical predictions of deviatoric stress (normalized with initial
488 preconsolidation pressure) versus axial strain, shown in Fig. 11b, are in acceptable agreement
489 with the experimental results.

490 In the case of $OCR=2$, the model predicts the failure strength properly in the stress-strain
491 space, while it fails to follow the stress path closely. Moreover, introducing the non-associated
492 flow rule does not help the model to simulate the behavior of the NC sample reasonably. Ling
493 et al. (2002) attributed this to the clay's softening behavior and suggested that a kinematic
494 hardening approach may resolve the discrepancies. Since the BS plasticity theory cannot adjust
495 the prediction of the behavior of NC samples, the simulations could be improved by using more
496 sophisticated BSs as well as using a destructuration hardening rule. Employing a more flexible
497 RH rule can also be helpful in generating more precise simulations.

Fig. 11. Comparison of BS-CLAY1 predictions for Boston blue clay

498 6.3. Lower Cromer till

499 The compression triaxial tests on anisotropically consolidated samples of Lower Cromer till
 500 (Gens, 1982) are also used to evaluate the model performance. The low plasticity glacial till
 501 samples were obtained from the Norfolk coast in the UK where the deposit had been part of
 502 the North Sea Drift. This sandy clay has a liquid limit and a plastic limit of 25% and 13%,
 503 respectively. Gens (1982) performed his experiments on reconstituted samples which were

504 taken from uniform specimens, and hence, the variability of this natural material was
505 overlooked.

506 Fig. 12 shows the BS-CLAY1 predictions of undrained anisotropic shearing of Lower
507 Cromer till samples corresponding to tests at different OCRs. Fig. 12a illustrates that for LOC
508 and HOC samples the model predictions of anisotropic stress paths are qualitatively and
509 quantitatively consistent with the experimental results. For the test at OCR=1, the model
510 prediction has a notable difference with the test measurements, and the proposed model is
511 unable to reproduce the softening behaviour, same as the simulations in Yang et al. (2015b).
512 Moreover, similar to the case of Boston blue clay for the OCR=2, the model shows a poor
513 simulation in stress space, while it has captured the failure strength in stress-strain space,
514 properly. However, the proposed model shows promising performance in simulating the HOC
515 samples.

Fig. 12. Comparison of BS-CLAY1 predictions for Lower Cromer till

516

517 7. Conclusion

518 A new anisotropic constitutive model has been developed within the critical state based
519 constitutive modeling framework. The new model is formulated based on a rotational
520 hardening rule and the bounding surface plasticity concept to simultaneously capture the fabric
521 anisotropy effects and the nonlinearity of soil responses before triggering the yield criterion.
522 For the BS extension, a step-be-step novel framework is employed that enhanced the prediction
523 capabilities of simple models with elliptical yield surfaces. The proposed framework is unique
524 in its own way since in addition to capturing the nonlinear behaviour inside the BS, it produces
525 desirable simulations for highly overconsolidated clays without the need to add more
526 complications to the model (i.e. non-elliptical yield surface with additional parameters). The
527 proposed framework includes a new modified method has been proposed to find the projection
528 center which significantly improved the model performance for stiff clays. The second
529 component of the proposed framework is a new concept to modify the BS configuration while
530 the stress state varies within the BS. Moreover, to enhance the model capabilities in simulating
531 the HOC samples, a non-associated flow rule is also adopted. The new model, BS-CLAY1, has

532 six additional parameters compared to its preceding model, which only two of them need
533 calibration through simulations of experimental data and the other four parameters can be
534 determined using the provided relations using the value of OCR. The numerical
535 implementation of the model was developed via an explicit Euler Forward integration scheme
536 for the stress states inside the BS and an implicit Euler Backward integration scheme for the
537 stress states on the BS. The model was then employed for prediction of the responses of three
538 different anisotropically consolidated clayey soils at different OCRs. The comparison of model
539 predictions against experimental data particularly illustrated the enhanced capabilities of the
540 model in capturing the responses of LOC to HOC soils. Since the developments in this paper
541 preserve some of the key original features of the S-CLAY1 model, there could be shortfalls in
542 the accuracy of simulations in the cases of both stress path and stress-strain responses,
543 particularly for normally consolidated (NC) samples. Although the adopted non-associated
544 flow rule provides notably better predictions for tests over NC soils, employing a non-elliptical
545 yield surface and developing a more flexible rotational hardening rule can address most of the
546 deficiencies associated with simple elliptical models.

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550 **Appendix**

551 The plastic modulus of the BS is achieved from consistency condition which requires that
 552 the stress state must remain on the BS during the plastic straining. The mathematical expression
 553 of the consistency condition is

$$\dot{F} = \frac{\partial F}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{ij}} d\bar{\sigma}_{ij} + \frac{\partial F}{\partial \alpha_{ij}^d} d\alpha_{ij}^d + \frac{\partial F}{\partial \bar{p}'_m} d\bar{p}'_m = 0 \quad (1a)$$

554 which can be rewritten in the following form

$$\dot{F} = \frac{\partial F}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{ij}} d\bar{\sigma}_{ij} + \frac{\partial F}{\partial \alpha_{ij}^d} d\alpha_{ij}^d + \frac{\partial F}{\partial \bar{p}'_m} \frac{d\bar{p}'_m}{d\varepsilon_v^p} d\varepsilon_v^p = 0 \quad (2a)$$

555 According to hardening rules (Eqs. (5), (6) and (7)), we have

$$\frac{d\bar{p}'_m}{d\varepsilon_v^p} = \frac{v\bar{p}'_m}{\lambda - \kappa} \quad (3a)$$

556

$$\begin{aligned} d\alpha_{ij}^d &= \mu \left(\left[\frac{3\bar{\sigma}_{ij}^d}{4\bar{p}'} - \alpha_{ij}^d \right] \langle d\varepsilon_v^p \rangle + \beta \left[\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{ij}^d}{3\bar{p}'} - \alpha_{ij}^d \right] d\varepsilon_a^p \right) \\ &= \mu \left(\left[\frac{3\bar{\sigma}_{ij}^d}{4\bar{p}'} - \alpha_{ij}^d \right] < \frac{1}{K_p} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{kl}} d\bar{\sigma}_{kl} \frac{\partial G}{\partial \bar{p}'} \right. \\ &\quad \left. > + \beta \left[\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{ij}^d}{3\bar{p}'} - \alpha_{ij}^d \right] \frac{1}{K_p} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{kl}} d\bar{\sigma}_{kl} \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{mn}^d} \right) \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{mn}^d} \right)} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (4a)$$

557 Eqs. (4a) can be rewritten in the following form

$$\begin{aligned}
 d\alpha_{ij}^d &= \left(\frac{\partial \alpha_{ij}^d}{\partial \varepsilon_v^p} < \frac{1}{\bar{K}_p} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{kl}} d\bar{\sigma}_{kl} \frac{\partial G}{\partial \bar{p}'} \right. \\
 &> \left. + \frac{\partial \alpha_{ij}^d}{\partial \varepsilon_d^p} \frac{1}{\bar{K}_p} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{kl}} d\bar{\sigma}_{kl} \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{mn}^d} \right) \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{mn}^d} \right)} \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{5a}$$

558 Putting Eqs. (3a), and (5a) in the consistency condition, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial F}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{ij}} d\bar{\sigma}_{ij} + \frac{\partial F}{\partial \alpha_{ij}^d} \left(\frac{\partial \alpha_{ij}^d}{\partial \varepsilon_v^p} < \frac{1}{\bar{K}_p} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{kl}} d\bar{\sigma}_{kl} \frac{\partial G}{\partial \bar{p}'} \right. \\
 &> \left. + \frac{\partial \alpha_{ij}^d}{\partial \varepsilon_d^p} \frac{1}{\bar{K}_p} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{kl}} d\bar{\sigma}_{kl} \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{mn}^d} \right) \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{mn}^d} \right)} \right) \\
 &+ \frac{\delta F}{\delta \bar{p}'_m} \frac{v\bar{p}'_m}{\lambda - \kappa} \left(\frac{1}{\bar{K}_p} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{kl}} d\bar{\sigma}_{kl} \frac{\partial G}{\partial \bar{p}'} \right) = 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{6a}$$

559 After some simplifications, the plastic modulus of bounding surface can be obtained as

$$\bar{K}_p = - \frac{\partial F}{\partial \alpha_{ij}^d} \left(\frac{\partial \alpha_{ij}^d}{\partial \varepsilon_v^p} \left\langle \frac{\partial G}{\partial \bar{p}'} \right\rangle + \frac{\partial \alpha_{ij}^d}{\partial \varepsilon_d^p} \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \frac{\partial G}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{ij}^d} \frac{\partial G}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{ij}^d}} \right) - \frac{\partial F}{\partial \bar{p}'_m} \frac{v\bar{p}'_m}{\lambda - \kappa} \frac{\partial G}{\partial \bar{p}'} \tag{7a}$$

560 where the \bar{K}_p is used besides the Eqs. (9) and (10) to determine the plastic modulus of the SS,

561 and therefore, to calculate the elastoplastic stiffness tensor at the current SS.

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